

Comparative Screening of the Nutritive Composition and Serum Nutrient Levels of Rats Weaned with Rice (*Oryza spp*) - Beniseed (*Sesame indicum*) Flour Blends

Esther C. Nwaoha

Department of Biochemistry, College of Biological Sciences, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Victor M. Ahur

Department of Veterinary Physiology, College of Veterinary Medicine, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Michael O. Nwankwo

Department of Biochemistry, College of Biological Sciences, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Nwoha, E.C., Ahur, V.M. & Nwankwo, M.O. (2023). Comparative Screening of the Nutritive Composition and Serum Nutrient Levels of Rats Weaned with Rice (*Oryza spp*) - Beniseed (*Sesame indicum*) Flour Blends. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 1099-1109. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).103](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).103)

Abstract:

Weaning foods should complement the nourishment the baby receives from milk. This study was carried out to evaluate the nutritional value of Rice-Beniseed (R-B) flour-blends in rats' pups. The objective of the study was to determine the Nutritive value of Rice-Beniseed flour blends of rats' pups weaned with different ratios of the flour-blends. First, mature female and male rats in the ratio of 2:1 were mated to produce pups used in the analyses. The pups were randomly distributed into five groups of five rats and were fed with the experimental (Rice-Beniseed) blends. Group 1 was fed with a standard weaning meal, groups 2, 3, 4 and 5 were fed *ad lib* with Rice-Beniseed blends (after proximate analysis for nutritive content) in

the ratio of 30:70, 50:50, 60:40 and 70:30 respectively. All treatments lasted for 21 days, after which their blood was collected for haematological and biochemical analyses. The results showed carbohydrate (71.76 %) and moisture content (14.75 %) of rice to be higher than beniseed with values of 18.74 and 8.24 % respectively. The crude proteins (23.19 %), crude fibre (11.47 %) and fats (36.40%) content in beniseed was more than doubled compared to that in rice with 9.38 %, 1.339 % and 2.41 % for crude protein, crude fibre, and fats contents respectively. Percentage weight change in pups was highest ($26.31 \pm 1.03\%$) and least ($8.69 \pm 2.32\%$) in the 50:50 and 60:40 rice-beniseed groups on day 7. Percentage weight change of pups on day 14 showed that groups fed with 70:30 and 50:50 ratios with the highest ($37.24 \pm 0.47\%$) and least ($6.16 \pm 1.14\%$) weight gain respectively. Hence, 70:30 (Rice-Beniseed blend) meal produced the best growth index (weight increase) and was potentially viable for the formulation of infant weaning formula amidst appreciable performance of all other ratios.

Keywords: weaning meal, beniseed, rice, flour-blends, ration.

Introduction

The growth and survival of infants after the recommended period of exclusive breastfeeding

of Six (6) months depend on the nutritional quality of the weaning food (Yomin, 2020). Breast milk is a sole and sufficient source of

nutrition during the first 6 months of infant life. It contains all the nutrients and immunological factors that infants require to maintain optimal health and growth. Thus weaning foods should complement the nourishment the baby receives from milk, rather than replacing it.

Malnutrition such as protein-energy-malnutrition (PEM) is a serious health problem in developing countries like Nigeria. In many indigent communities in Nigeria, low-cost high-protein diet is still a challenge due to the high level of poverty and hunger (Akinyetun., *et al* 2021). Hence the high cost of commercial feeding formulae is a disincentive to acquire a nutritious weaning meal which could be a major cause of infant malnourishment and mortality in post-neonatal infants and pre-school children (Zakpaa, 2010)

Therefore, a decline in the lactation coupled with early supplementation or replacement of breast milk with wrongly and un-hygienically constituted meals could have serious implications on the nutritional status of infants. (Umar & Oche, 2013) The major criteria for a good-quality weaning food are high balanced-protein content, high caloric value per unit of food volume, soft texture with low fiber content, adequate vitamin and mineral contents, and absence of anti-nutritional factors (Umar & Oche, 2013). With these requirements kept in mind, weaning foods are usually formulated using a mixture of cereals and legumes which guarantee a proper balanced diet. Thus, cereals such as rice and beniseed whose nutrient compositions are recommended as foods for fighting hunger and infant malnutrition can be blended by mothers as alternative weaning formula for infants. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the nutritional value of Rice-Beniseed flour blends as a weaning formula in rat pups.

Materials and Methods

Rice, Beniseeds and standard feed

Rice, Beniseed and standard formula (Cerelac®) were purchased at the Wadata market of Makurdi metropolis.

Experimental Animals

The breeding rats were sourced from the local breeder in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria, and bred for 28 days in plastic cages that was maintained at room temperature of $25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a 12-hour light/dark cycle where the pups were produced. Twenty-five (25) albino rat pups of both sexes used for the experiments were allowed to attain weaning age of 21 days before they were separated from the dam and employed for the experiment. The experiment was conducted according to international guiding principles for biomedical research involving animals (CIOMS, 1985).

Preparation of Rice-Beniseeds Rations

The rice grains were cleaned and sorted out, washed and dry-milled and sieved to obtain a fine rice flour and packaged in a polythene bag and stored until needed. The beniseeds treated similarly with rice except roasting before milling. The rice-beniseed flour blends were thereafter mixed into the following 4 different rice to beniseed ratios 50:50, 70:30, 60:40 and 30:70 respectively.

Proximate Analysis

Proximate analysis of the commercial standard formula (Normal Control Group – Group 1) and the experimental blends were carried out using the standard procedure of AOAC (2002) to ascertain their individual nutritional values.

Experimental Design

Twenty-five rat pups were grouped into 5 groups (1-5) of 5 pups each. Group 1 pups were fed standard commercial weaning formula, whilst groups 4 to 5 were fed rice-beniseeds flour blends ratios 50:50, 70:30, 60:40 and 30:70 for groups 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively. Feeding lasted for 21 days where weekly weights were taken. Twelve (12) hours after the last feeding, all rats were bled into sample bottles for the analysis of haematological and biochemical growth index parameters.

Determination of Haematological Parameters

The haematocrit or PCV was determined by the standard microhaematocrit method as described

by Coles (1986). The RBC Count was determined using the haemocytometer method as described by Schalm *et al.* (1975). The Haemoglobin concentration was determined by Drabkin's cyanomethaemoglobin method as described by Chessbrough (2005). The WBC count was determined by the improved Neubauer method as described by Chessbrough (2005) and Differential WBC counts were determined by method described Chessbrough (2005).

Determination of Biochemical Parameters

Serum potassium, sodium, chloride, bicarbonate, total and ionized calcium were measured with ion selective electrode principle using XI-921D electrolyte analyser- (Caretium medical instrument Co., Ltd, Shenzhen China). Colorimetric method was applied to measure serum Total protein, albumin, Magnesium, inorganic phosphate and glucose levels following the insert methodology of commercially prepared chemistry kits by Agappe diagnostics Switzerland. Absorbance was read using NB201-C semi-auto chemistry analyser, Caretium medical instrument Co., Ltd, Shenzhen China).

Determination of Feed Efficiency Ratio (FER)

Feed efficiency ratio was calculated using the following formula.

$$FER = \frac{\text{Gain in body weight (g)}}{\text{Feed intake (g)}} \quad (1)$$

Results

Nutrient Composition of Rice, Beniseeds, Standard Formular (Feed) and the Different Formulated Rations.

The proximate analysis of rice and Beniseed revealed that Rice has a high percentage of carbohydrates (71.76%), but low percentage of crude protein (9.38%), crude fibre (1.339%) and fats (2.41%), when compared to beniseed which has low percentage of carbohydrate (18.74%), and high percentage of crude protein (23.19), crude fiber (11.47%), and fats (36.40%) as shown in Table 1. The proximate analysis on the different food ratio revealed that the carbohydrate content of the RB70:30 food ratio group is significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than all the other food ratio group (71.98%) while the protein, fibre and fat content of RB30:70 is significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than the other food ratio group (19.00, 4.60, 7.89%) respectively as shown in Table 2.

Table 1. Proximate Analysis of Rice and Beniseed (Sesame)

Feed	Percentage Composition					
	Carbohydrate	Crude protein	Crude fibre	Fat	Moisture	Ash
Rice	71.76	9.38	1.33	2.41	14.75	1.37
Beniseed	18.74	23.19	11.47	36.40	8.24	1.96

Table 2. Proximate Analysis of the Various Meal Compositions of Different Ratios

Feed	Percentage (%) Composition						
	Carbohydrate	Crude protein	Crude fibre	Fats	Moisture	Ash	Energy (Kcal.)
Control	55.67	20.56	5.11	3.07	8.13	7.46	332.55
R-B 30:70	60.47	19.00	4.60	7.89	3.74	4.30	388.89
R-B50:50	64.26	17.94	2.44	7.10	4.19	4.07	392.70
R-B 60:40	67.98	16.56	2.32	4.24	5.66	3.08	376.32
R-B 70:30	71.98	13.94	1.75	4.18	6.17	2.81	381.30

Note: The formula is Energy (in Kcal) = 4 x (Proteins and carbohydrates mass in grammes) + 9 x mass of fat in grammes. Carbohydrates provide 4 calories per grammes, protein provides 4 calories per grammes, and fat provides 9 calories per grammes.

Effects of Feeding Rat Pups with Rice-Beniseed Flour Blends on Weekly Digestibility Index

At week one the digestibility result revealed that the RB 30:70 (39.22%) digested better than other food ratio groups as compared to the control group (30.65%), this pattern seemed consistent with weeks 2 and 3 as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Weekly Digestibility Result of the Different Group for 3 Weeks

Week	Sample	Percent (%) Composition					
		Carbohydrate	Crude Protein	Fat/oil	Ash	Moisture	Crude fibre
1	Control	30.65	26.75	0.45	11.55	9.01	15.03
	R-B 30:70	39.22	17.50	6.89	15.40	8.22	12.77
	R-B 50:50	41.36	16.63	4.89	16.28	7.85	12.99
	R-B 60:40	42.97	17.06	5.13	16.35	8.04	10.45
	R-B 70:30	41.81	17.50	6.99	13.97	8.02	11.71
2	Control	32.52	28.44	0.53	12.55	9.49	16.47
	R-B 30:70	38.29	18.37	6.17	18.48	8.35	10.34
	R-B 50:50	38.38	17.50	8.18	13.34	7.02	15.93
	R-B 60:40	36.26	17.94	6.96	19.85	6.85	12.14
	R-B 70:30	43.52	16.62	8.66	14.26	7.07	9.86
3	Control	35.38	24.06	5.81	16.30	8.42	10.03
	R-B 30:70	43.61	18.37	6.70	15.03	7.43	8.86
	R-B 50:50	38.03	15.31	9.08	18.39	9.66	9.03
	R-B 60:40	44.25	13.13	10.57	17.19	7.00	7.86
	R-B 70:30	41.39	19.69	10.13	15.96	7.15	5.68

Effect of the Different Food Ratios on the Body Weight of Rats

The percentage change in weight was significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) in the 50:50 food ratio group ($26.31 \pm 1.03\%$) compared to the control group (8.48 ± 1.21) after 7 days of feeding the formula whereas, the 60:40 food ratio group had a significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) weight gain ($8.69 \pm 2.32\%$) as represented in Table 4 (Appendix 1). However, the weight gain of the 50:50 ratio was significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) ($6.16 \pm 1.41\%$) at day 14 of feeding the food ratio, where ratio 70:30 feed formula significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) by $37.24 \pm 0.47\%$ higher than other food ratio group but less compared to the percentage weight gain of the control group ($46.86 \pm 1.53\%$). The percentage change in weight at day 21 of all the food ratio groups was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) than the control group ($22.84 \pm 1.16\%$). However, an overall $95.61 \pm 1.78\%$ weight gain between days 0-21 was observed in the control group, meanwhile, 70:30 food ratio group gain an overall weight of

($63.53 \pm 1.53\%$) which was close in percentage weight gain in the control group than in other food ratio groups.

Effects of the Different Feed Ratios on the Haematological Parameters of Rat Pups

Haematology results showed Group 2 (R-B 30:70), Group 4 (R-B 60:40), Group 5 (R-B 70:30), all have statistically and significantly increased ($p < 0.05$) PCV when compared to the Normal control ($39.78 \pm 0.47\%$); where Group 3 (R-B 50:50) showed a significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) PCV of $37.93 \pm 0.39\%$ compared to the Normal control animals. Group 4 (R-B 60:40) showed a significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) PCV value of 48.10 ± 0.49 followed by Group 5 (R-B 70:30) with a PCV of $46.27 \pm 0.50\%$. Erythrocytes values showed no significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the food ratio groups and the control group.

The outcome of the haemoglobin result showed Group 2 (R-B 30:70 15.65 ± 0.23), Group 3 (R-B 50:50 12.64 ± 0.13 g/L), Group 4 (R-B 60:40

16.03±0.16 g/L), Group 5 (R-B70:30 15.43±0.17 g/L) all have a significant difference when compared to the Control (13.26±0.16 g/L). However, Group 4 showed the highest value of haemoglobin, followed by Group 2 and 5, while Group 3 has the lowest value of the haemoglobin when compared to the Normal control group as shown in Table 5 (Appendix 1). Furthermore, leucocytes values revealed Group 4 (RB 6040, 11.17±0.33), and Group 5 (RB 70:30, 11.07±0.42 x 10⁹/L showed a significant increase (p<0.05) when compared to the control group (9.25±0.26 x 10⁹/L), whilst Group 2 (7.68±0.35 x 10⁹/L) and Group 3 (7.19±0.230 x 10⁹/L) showed a significantly decreased (p<0.05) Hb when also compared to the Control (see Table 5 – Appendix 1).

Haematological parameters also revealed lymphocytes values to be significantly different between the food ratio groups and control. Group 2 (56.01±0.39 %) and Group 3 (57.99±0.65%) showed a significant decrease (p<0.05) when compared to the control while Group 4 (69.82±0.88 %) and Group 5 (70.30±0.74 %) showed a significant increase when compared to the control (68.23±0.62) as shown in Table 5 (Appendix 1). Neutrophil count of Group 2 (40.17±0.40 %) and Group 3 (35.81±0.41 %) were observed to be significantly higher (p<0.05) when compared to the control (25.46±0.69). Monocytes values of Group 2 (2.32±0.40 %) and group 4 (3.94±0.97 %) showed significant decrease (p<0.05) when compared to the control (4.33±0.73 %) but showed no significant difference across other groups. Determination of Neutrophils revealed only group 2 and 3 that has significantly higher neutrophils values when compared to the Control. Similarly, results of monocytes evaluation showed only group 2 to have significantly lower values compared to the rest of the groups. Eosinophils value for group 3 (0.99±0.09) and 4 (1.02±0.07) are slightly higher than that of food ratio group 2 (0.83 ±0.06) and 5 (0.61±0.03), but lower than the control (1.05±0.06 %).

Effects of the Different Feed Rations on the Biochemical Parameters of Rat Pups

Biochemical parameters ((Table 6 – Appendix 1) revealed K⁺ values of Group 2 (7.05±0.40 mmol/L) and group 5 (7.05±0.28 mmol/L) to be significantly decreased (p<0.05) when compared to the control (9.03±0.37 mmol/L) but showed no significant difference across any other Group. Groups 2 (143.78±0.76 mmol/L), group 3 (140.68 ± 0.42 mmol/L), group 4 (142.98±0.22 mmol/L) showed a significantly decreased (p<0.05) Na⁺ when compared to the control (147.80 ± 0.33 mmol/L), while group 5 (146.82 ± 0.42) showed a significant increase (p<0.05) when compared to the food ratio groups 2, 3, and 4.

Analysis of Chloride ions showed Group 2 (102.24±1.55 mmol/L) and Group 3 (103.22±0.59 mmol/L) to be significantly decreased (p<0.05) when compared to the Control Group (106.32±0.86 mmol/L) but showed no significant difference across any other group, while group 4 (106.54 ± 0.51 mmol/L) and group 5 (106.90±0.31 mmol/L) showed a significant increase when compared to group 2 and group 3. Biochemical results also showed Bicarbonate ion to be significantly different between the control and all the food ratio groups. The Group 2 (12.52±2.27 mmol/L), group 3 (11.36±1.51 mmol/L), group 4 (13.3±2.65 mmol/L) and group 5 (13.7±1.94 mmol/L) have significantly decreased (p<0.05) when compared to the control group (19.52±0.53 mmol/L).

Furthermore, total Calcium ions of Group 5 (1.87±0.09 mmol/L) had a significant difference with the control group, it showed a significant increase (p<0.05) when compared to the control group (1.50±0.06). Also, on ionized Calcium only the group 2 (0.86±0.06 mmol/L) had a significant difference (p<0.05) with the control group (0.73±0.04 mmol/L). Inorganic Phosphorus values revealed a scientifically significant difference only between the Control Group and the Food Ratio Group 5. Group 5 (4.20±0.32 mg/dL) showed a significant decrease (p<0.05) when compared to the control

(5.42 ± 0.07 mg/dL) and other Food Ratio Groups (see Table 6 – Appendix 1).

Analysis of macromolecules like glucose and total protein revealed thus, for Glucose Group 2 (with 6.52 ± 0.57 mmol/L) showed a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the Control Group (4.32 ± 0.75 mmol/L) and other Food Ratio groups of Group 4 (4.12 ± 0.51 mmol/L), and Group 5 (3.22 ± 0.68 mmol/L), whilst Total protein values of Group 4 (69.68 ± 1.74 g/L) and Group 5 (74.00 ± 3.14 g/L) showed a scientifically significant increase ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the Control Group (57.90 ± 2.18 mmol/L). Similarly, determination of the protein albumin showed that Food Ratio Group 5 (35.66 ± 1.02 g/L) had a statistically significant difference with the other groups. It showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the Control (30.66 ± 1.54 g/L), and the other Food Ratio Group 2 (31.74 ± 1.15 g/L), Group 3 (30.48 ± 1.19 g/L) and Group 4 (31.42 ± 0.79 g/L).

Discussion

The result of this work showed that the protein contents for all the feed formulation meet the normal required standards set for infant diet (FAO/WHO, 1992). The high fat content obtained in R-B 30:70 and R-B 50:50 may be due to the fact that beniseed is an oilseed, and both food ratios has a higher percentage ratio of beniseed content and the fat content in the diets meets the normal required standards recommended for infant diet (FAO/WHO, 1992).

The carbohydrate content of all the food ratio groups were higher when compared to the control, with the 5th group (R-B70:30) having the highest percentage of carbohydrate (71.98 %), this may be due to the increased ratio of the rice in the feed formulation, as the higher the rice content the higher the carbohydrates level, since rice is very rich in carbohydrate (Fri and Backer, 2004). However, the percentage level of carbohydrate found in R-B 30:70 (60.47 %) meets the normal required standard for infants, as the Institute of Medicine encourages infants

up to 6 months of age to consume at least 60 grammes of carbohydrates (Erin Coleman, 2018). The crude fibre contents of the R-B 30:70, R-B 50:50, R-B 60:40 and R-B 70:30 are 4.60%, 2.44%, 2.32% and 1.75% respectively. These values are low when compared to that of the control diet. A very low level of fibre content in weaning food has been recommended (Imtiaz, 2011). The low fibre content will encourage high digestibility and absorption of the diets by the infants. For moisture, and ash contents, the moisture content of all the diets were lower than that of the control diet. However, these values still fall within the expected range for weaning diet which must not exceed 10%. The ash content of the diets was lower than that of the control diet but falls within the recommended value for weaning food which must not exceed 5%.

During the 21-days experimental period the adaptation of the animals fed on each dietary sample and utilization of each diet were studied. Food and water were given to them *ad libitum*. The animals that fed on the R-B 50:50 diets were found to become leaner and lost weight at the 2nd week of been fed with the Rice-Beniseed 50:50 food ratio, Changes were observed on their skin and in their consumption rate. Loss of weight was dramatic from average weight gain of 26.31% at day 7 to 22.34% at day 21, though no death was recorded. On the other hand, the animals fed with other diets increased in weight especially in the commercial diet group followed by the Rice-Beniseed 70:30 food ratio which did better in weight gain and in the consumption of the feed when compared to other food ratio group, this could be because of the low fibre (1.7%) and fats (4.18%) content in the R-B 70:30 food ratio, as low fibre aids proper digestibility and absorption of consumed food. The high carbohydrate 71.98 content also contributed to the level of weight gain in that group as its carbohydrate level is higher than the other food ratio groups, then by the R-B 60:40 and lastly by R-B 30:70 as shown in table 4.

After the animals were fed for 21 days with the weaning meals of different ratios for the different groups, their blood samples were collected for haematological analysis, all the

groups did well with the haematological parameters though the group 3, which is R-S50:50 had the lowest values of PCV (37.93%), other RBC (6.61%), Hb (12.64%), and WBC (7.19%), when compared to the control group and food ratio groups, but their haematological parameters all met the standard of that of children of the weaning age bracket. This shows that the Rice-Beniseed weaning meal supports the need and development of children of the weaning age. Blood examination is a good way of assessing the health status of animals as it plays a vital role in physiological, nutritional and pathological status of an organism (Ehrlich, *et al.*, 2021). Both muscle tissues and neurons are considered electric tissues of the body. Muscles and neurons are activated by electrolyte activity between the extracellular fluid and intracellular fluid and the balance of these electrolytes in the body is essential for normal function of the cells and organs (Coso *et al.*, 2008). Electrolytes occur in large quantities in both extracellular and intracellular fluids, with respect to serum sodium and chloride levels. Muscle contraction is dependent on the presence of electrolytes like; calcium (Ca^{2+}), sodium (Na^+), and potassium (K^+), without sufficient levels of these key electrolytes, muscle weakness or severe muscle contractions may occur in children (Gałęska *et al* 2022). However, for potassium, only group 2 and 5 showed a scientific significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the control group, the rats in group 3 and 4 showed no significant difference as compared to the control group, while for sodium and chloride, the group 5 had no significant difference when compared to the control though lower in value, thereby showing they fell within the standard value for those electrolyte. Sodium regulates the total amount of water in the body and the transmission of sodium in and out of individual cells plays a critical role in the body functions (Hanukoglu & Hanukoglu, 2016).

Many processes in the body, especially in the brain, nervous system, and muscles, require electrical signals for communication (Ighodaro, 2012). The movement of sodium is critical in generation of these electrical signals. Too much or too little sodium therefore can cause cells to

malfunction, and extremes in the blood sodium levels (too much or too little) can be fatal (Ighodaro, 2012). Reduction in serum Na & Cl below the clinically accepted range is indicative of dehydration and shock, while an increase in serum albumin is indicative of stress on the liver organ and a reduction of the same is indicative of chronic liver diseases (Coso *et al.*, 2008), this was however not the case in the present study as the albumin level of all the food ratio groups fell within the normal standard range of 30-51g/L, however there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference between the group 5 and the control group. Calcium is a major structural element in bones and teeth. It is necessary to stabilize or allow for optimal activity of a number of proteins and enzymes. The binding of calcium to the protein, troponin-c, initiates a series of steps that lead to muscle contraction. The binding of calcium to the protein, calmodulin activates enzymes that breakdown muscle glycogen, which provides energy for muscle contraction (Hargreaves, M., & Spriet, L. L. 2020). Also the binding of calcium ions is required for the activation of the seven "vitamin K-dependent" clotting factors in the coagulation cascade, with the exception of group 5 (1.87mmol/l), which showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference with the control, rats fed on the other experimental diets has no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference with the control, indicating that the feed may be a rich source of calcium, (Hargreaves, M., & Spriet, L. L. 2020

The magnesium for all the other groups had no significant difference with the control hence the feed had no effect on the magnesium level, though all the values fell within the clinical standard for infants. The phosphorus, glucose and total protein, though had significant difference but fell within the clinical standard values for infants, this shows that the feeds supports the electrolytes levels in the right proportion in infants of weaning age.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that local resources have great potentials in the formulation and preparation of

infant weaning foods since most Nigerian children are already accustomed to weaning preparations from rice, or other cereals, the greatest task was to improve the protein contents of this weaning food. This is achieved by the addition of beniseed to rice.

This work also shows that the ratio of sesame in the feed actually has the ability to increase or decrease the protein and other nutritional contents of the formula, so depending on the values and levels of performance needed, the ratio of rice to sesame will then be decided on. It was thus concluded that, the food ratio of Rice-Beniseed 70:30 diet was potentially viable in the formulation of an infant weaning diet; though all the other ratio did well too. The implication of this finding is far reaching since all the components used in the formulation were obtained from local sources. This would indicate that the product would be cheaper and more accessible. When produced on a commercial scale, it will go a long way in ameliorating the usual symptoms of Protein-Energy Malnutrition (PEM) commonly prevalent in the developing country like Nigeria.

Recommendation

Quantitative phytochemical analysis should be performed on the individual meal ratios. This would give a clearer view of the percentage composition of each phytochemical contained in each group ratio, hence buttress studies on its potential properties for weaning meal preparation.

This research should be carried beyond this limit to see the effects of these group ratios each on the outcome of serving as the chosen ration for weaning meal preparation.

Toxicity study on the meal should be studied too.

Ethical approval

The ethical consideration was obtained from the ethical committee of college of veterinary

medicine teaching hospital, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi, Nigeria.

Funding

This piece of work did not have any grant. It was carried out through the shared financial efforts of the contributors.

Author's contribution

The authors confirm contributions to the paper as follows: the first author wrote the paper, the second author contributed data and performed the analysis. the third author conceptualized, designed and proof-read as well as serve as the corresponding author.

Conflict of Interest

The authors of this work have no conflict of interest whatsoever before, during and after this study.

References

- Akinyetun, T. S., Alausa, J. A., Odeyemi, D. D., & Ahoton, A. S. (2021). Assessment of the prevalence of multidimensional poverty in Nigeria: Evidence from Oto/Ijanikin, Lagos State. *Journal of Sustainable Social Change*, 13(2), 3.
- Horwitz, W. & AOAC International. (2002). *Official methods of analysis of aoac international* (17. ed. current through revision). AOAC International.
- Cheesbrough, M. (2009) *District Laboratory practice in tropical countries*. 2nd ed. Cambridge university press.
- CLSI. (2000). *Procedure for Determining Packed Cell Volume by the Microhematocrit Method*. Approved Standard—Third Edition. CLSI document H07-A3. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. Retrieved from https://clsi.org/media/2392/h07a3e_sample.pdf
- CLSI. (2007). *Reference Leukocyte (WBC) Differential Count (Proportional) and Evaluation of*

Instrumental Methods; Approved Standard—Second Edition. CLSI document H20-A2. Wayne, PA: Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. Retrieved from https://clsi.org/media/1400/h20a2_sample.pdf

Coso, J. D., Estevez, E., Baquero, R. A., & Mora-Rodriguez, R. (2008). Anaerobic performance when rehydrating with water or commercially available sports drinks during prolonged exercise in the heat. *Applied physiology, nutrition, and metabolism = Physiologie appliquee, nutrition et metabolisme*, 33(2), 290–298. <https://doi.org/10.1139/H07-188>

Council for International Organisations of Medical Sciences (1985). *International guiding principles for biomedical research involving animals*. Proceedings of the November 2003 International Workshop.

Ehrlich, M., Luiz, B. J., Mendes, C. G., & Lacerda, W. A. (2021). Triggering factors and critical thresholds for landslides in Rio de Janeiro-RJ, Brazil. *Natural Hazards*, 107, 937–952. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-021-04616-w>

Gałęska, E., Wrzecińska, M., Kowalczyk, A., & Araujo, J. P. (2022). Reproductive Consequences of Electrolyte Disturbances in Domestic Animals. *Biology*, 11(7), 1006. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biology11071006>

Hanukoglu, I., & Hanukoglu, A. (2016). Epithelial sodium channel (ENaC) family: Phylogeny, structure-function, tissue distribution, and associated inherited diseases. *Gene*, 579(2), 95–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2015.12.061>

Hargreaves, M., & Spriet, L. L. (2020). Skeletal muscle energy metabolism during exercise. *Nature metabolism*, 2(9), 817–828. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42255-020-0251-4>

Imtiaz, H., BurhanUddin, M., & Gulzar, M. A. (2011). Evaluation of weaning foods formulated

from germinated wheat and mungbean from Bangladesh. *African journal of food science*, 5(17), 897–903. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJFS11.180>

Ighodaro, O. M. (2012). Evaluation study on Nigerian species of *Musa paradisiaca* peels. *Researcher*, 4(8), 17–20.

Umar, A. S., & Oche, M. O. (2013). Breastfeeding and weaning practices in an urban slum, North Western Nigeria. *Int J Trop Dis Health*, 3(2), 114–25. <https://doi.org/10.9734/IJTDRH/2013/1337>

Praful, B.G., & Darshan, P.G. (2003). *Textbook of Medical Laboratory Technology*. Bhalani Publishing House.

WHO/FAO. (1992). Energy and Protein Requirements. Report of a joint FAO/WHO. Expert consultation. *WHO Tech. Report Series*, 74, 86–98. Retrieved from <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/39527>

WHO/FAO. (1998). Preparation and the use of Food based diet Guidelines. Report of a joint Consultation. Geneva. Retrieved from <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42051>

World Health Organization. (2021). WHO global anaemia estimates. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/anaemia>

Yomin, V.Y. (2020). Study of pattern of foods given to the infants during weaning period in an urban field practice area in Vijayapura. Retrieved from <https://jhpn.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41043-020-0210-4>

Zakpaa, H. D., Mak-Mensah, E. E., & Adubofour, J. (2010). Production and Characterization of flour produced from ripe "apem" Plantain (*musa sapientum* L. var. *paradisiacal*; French horn) grown in Ghana. *Journal of Agricultural Biotechnology and Sustainable Development*, 2(6), 92.

Appendix 1

Table 4. Showing the Rate of Change in Body Weight.

Groups	Day 0 (g)	Day7 (g)	% change	Day 14 (g)	% change	Day21 (g)	% change	Overall % change
1 (Control)	25.30±0.25	27.43±0.25	8.48±1.21	40.28±0.30	46.86±1.53	49.47±0.31	22.84±1.16	95.61±1.78
2 (R-B 30:70)	51.99±0.38	56.72±0.21	9.14 ± 1.10	61.96±0.37	9.22 ± 0.42	66.40±0.51	7.17 ± 0.34	27.76±1.63
3 (R-B 50:50)	27.11±0.20	34.24±0.25	26.31±1.03	32.12±0.37	-6.16±1.41	33.16±0.49	3.28±1.82	22.34±1.86
4 (R-B 60:40)	25.26±0.39	27.42±0.25	8.69±2.32	29.92±0.54	9.17±2.46	33.16±0.49	9.52±2.85	29.66±2.81
5 (R-B 70:30)	50.27±0.31	56.17±0.31	11.75±0.86	77.09±0.47	37.24±0.47	82.20±0.59	6.67±1.36	63.53±1.53

Table 5. Showing Haematological Parameters

Groups	PCV (%)	RBC (x 10 ⁹ /L)	Hb (g/L)	WBC (x 10 ⁹ /L)	Lym. (%)	Neu. (%)	Mono. (%)	Eosin. (%)	Baso. (%)
1 (Control)	39.78±0.47	7.47±0.16	13.26±0.16	9.25±0.26 ^{b,c,d}	68.23±0.62	25.46±0.69	4.33±0.73	1.05 ±0.06	0.93 ±0.05
2 (R-B 30:70)	46.94 ±0.68 ^a	8.39±0.37	15.65±0.23 ^a	7.68 ±0.35 ^{a,d}	56.01±0.39 ^a	40.17 ±0.40 ^a	2.32 ±0.40 ^a	0.83 ±0.06 ^a	0.67±0.15 ^a
3 (R-B 50:50)	37.93 ±0.39 ^{a,b}	6.61±0.42 ^b	12.64±0.13 ^{a,b}	7.19±0.23 ^a	57.99±0.65 ^{a,b}	35.81±0.41 ^{a,b}	4.30±0.37	0.99±0.09	0.91±0.05 ^b
4 (R-B 60:40)	48.10±0.49 ^{a,c}	7.60±0.35	16.03±0.16 ^{a,c}	11.17±0.33 ^{a,b,c}	69.82±0.88 ^{a,b,c}	24.84±0.36 ^{b,c}	3.94±0.97 ^a	1.02±0.07 ^{a,b,c}	0.38±0.02 ^b
5 (R-B 70:30)	46.27±0.50 ^{a,c,d}	8.26±0.28 ^c	15.43±0.17 ^{a,c,d}	11.07±0.42 ^{a,b,c,d}	70.30±0.74 ^{a,b,c,d}	24.61±0.71 ^{b,c}	4.09±0.51	0.61±0.03 ^{a,b,c}	0.39±0.01 ^{a,d}

Key: PCV: packed cell volume, RBC: Red blood cell, Hb: Haemoglobin, WBC: White blood cell, Lym: Lymphocytes, Neu: Neutrophils, Mono: Monocytes, Eosin: Eosinophils, Baso: Basophils. Values are mean±SEM (Standard error of mean), n = 5. Values with different alphabet shows significance difference between each other. ^a*P* < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the control group. ^b*P* < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB3070 food ratio group. ^c*P* < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB5050 food ratio group. ^d*P* < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB6040 food ratio group.

Table 6. Serum Results showing Electrolytes, Glucose, Protein and Albumin result

Groups	K ⁺ (mmol/L)	Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	CL ⁻ (mmol/L)	HCO ₃ ⁻ (mmol/L)	TCa ²⁺ (mmol/L)	ICa ²⁺ (mmol/L)	Mg ²⁺ (mmol/L)	PO ₄ ²⁺ (mg/dl)	Glu (mmol/L)	TProt. (g/L)	Alb (g/L)
1 (Control)	9.03±0.37	147.80±0.33	106.32±0.86 ^b	19.52±0.53	1.50±0.06	0.73±0.04	1.16±0.07	5.42±0.07	4.32±0.75	57.90±2.18	30.66±1.54
2 (R-B 30:70)	7.05±0.40 ^a	143.78±0.76 ^a	102.24±1.55 ^a	12.52±2.27 ^a	1.68±0.12	0.86±0.06 ^a	1.25±0.002	5.31± 0.09	6.52±0.57 ^a	67.84±5.24	31.74±1.15
3 (R-B 50:50)	7.77±0.31	140.68±0.42 ^a	103.22±0.59 ^a	11.36±1.51 ^a	1.42±0.07	0.76±0.04	1.17±0.07	5.12±0.22	5.14±0.34	65.32±3.56	30.48±1.19
4 (R-B 60:40)	8.79±0.87 ^b	142.98±0.22 ^{a,c,d}	106.54±0.51 ^{b,c}	13.3±2.65 ^a	1.58±0.12	0.78±0.07	1.26±0.002	5.19±0.16	4.12±0.51 ^b	69.68±1.74 ^a	31.42±0.79
5 (R-B 70:30)	7.05±0.28 ^{a,d}	146.82 ±0.42 ^{c,d}	106.90±0.31 ^{b,c}	13.7±1.94 ^a	1.87±0.09 ^{a,c,d}	0.93±0.04 ^c	1.22±0.02	4.20±0.32 ^{a,b,c,d}	3.22±0.68 ^{b,c}	74.00±3.14 ^a	35.66±1.02 ^{a,b,c,d}

Key: K⁺ = Potassium, Na⁺ = Sodium, CL⁻ = Chloride, TCa²⁺ = Total calcium, ICa²⁺ = Ionized calcium, Mg²⁺ = Magnesium, Inorganic PO₄²⁺ = Inorganic Phosphate, Glu = Glucose, TProt. = Total Protein, Alb = Albumin. Values are mean±SEM (Standard error or mean), n = 5. Values with different alphabet shows significance difference between each other. ^aP < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the control group. ^bP < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB3070 food ratio group. ^cP < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB5050 food ratio group. ^dP < 0.05: significant difference in comparison with the RB6040 food ratio group.